

PROSPECTS FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF PUBLIC EDUCATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

At present, the development of countries is determined, first of all, by the quality level of their education system, since education is not only the most important sphere that forms the intellectual potential of a person, but also ensures the economic, social, and spiritual stability of society. Therefore, in the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy, the reform of the public education system, its reorganization in accordance with modern requirements, and the introduction of effective management mechanisms are defined as priority tasks. In the process of reforms being carried out in our country, fundamental changes are also taking place in the field of public education management. First of all, the phased removal of the education system from centralized management, free management of school activities on the ground, increasing the authority of the teacher's personality, and improving the mechanisms for monitoring the quality of education were recognized as urgent areas.

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1. Modernization of the education management system. In recent years, measures have been implemented in the public education system aimed at gradually moving away from centralized management, expanding the independence of schools, and increasing the professional responsibility of teachers. The restructuring of the Ministry of Public Education and the introduction of "School Coordination Headquarters" has accelerated the decision-making process and allowed for a reduction in management costs by more than 20%.

As a result of management reforms, digital systems regulating the educational process have been widely implemented. In particular, electronic document management has been launched through the platforms "my.edu.uz," "Kundalik," and "educational center." This process has quadrupled document flow, increased transparency and accountability.

By 2024, more than 90 percent of general education institutions in the country are using an electronic management system. In 2019, this figure was only 28 percent. Thus, over the past five years, a fundamental change has occurred in the management of general education institutions. The widespread introduction of digital management platforms has also shown positive results. According to the data studied within the framework of the study, 92% of schools actively use electronic systems in 2024. This made it possible to increase transparency in the educational process, monitor student attendance in real time, and apply a data-based approach to decision-making. At the same time, in regions where digital platforms have been implemented, it can be observed that the bureaucratic burden on teachers has been reduced by an average of 5 hours, which made it possible to allocate more time to the main activity of teachers - improving the quality of the educational process.

2. Increasing human capital and professional potential. The main idea of the education policy of New Uzbekistan is the development of human capital. Extensive reforms have been carried out to improve the professional qualifications of teachers and managerial personnel. Between 2018 and 2024, the number of teachers increased from 446,000 to 512,000, 80% of whom participated in professional development courses.

Significant changes are also observed in digital competencies: if in 2018 19% of teachers used e-learning platforms, then by 2024 this figure exceeded 70%. This means that teachers have strengthened their skills in applying their knowledge in the digital environment. Qualitative changes are also observed in the composition of managerial personnel: 64% of managers have special qualifications in modern management or educational management. This allows managing the system based on modern scientific approaches.

3. Public control and local initiatives. In this regard, the expansion of public participation in the management of the education system in New Uzbekistan is an important trend. By 2024, public councils operate in 80% of general education schools. Thanks to them, it became possible to attract local resources and expand the sponsorship system.

For example, in some regions, 10-15 percent of school budget funds are formed at the expense of local initiatives. This contributes to strengthening the material and technical base of schools and updating the educational environment.

Public participation has strengthened the principles of democracy in education management, ensuring openness and accountability. This has become a practical embodiment of the principle "For Human Dignity."

4. Quality of education and management effectiveness. During 2018-2024, Uzbekistan participated in international educational quality assessment programs (TIMSS, PISA) and improved its results by 11-13 points. At the same time, internal assessment systems and national standards have been updated.

The teacher development rate increased from 34 percent to over 80 percent, and the share of schools using e-governance increased from 28 percent to 92 percent. These results show that the qualitative changes in the system are in a stable direction.

At the same time, there are some issues in the system that require solutions:

Regional imbalance - in some remote areas, digital infrastructure is underdeveloped.

The problem of qualifications and motivation - the material incentives for teachers - is not yet the same in all regions.

Compliance of educational content with market requirements - some subject programs are insufficiently connected with practice.

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To solve these problems, it is necessary, based on the experience of Finland, South Korea, and Singapore, to expand the autonomy of school management, retraining personnel, and the deep implementation of digital management.

Conclusion

- In the context of the New Uzbekistan, the concept of managing the public education system is being radically updated. The transition from a centralized management model, the prioritization of human capital, and the transition to digital management constitute the main content of the reforms.

- rational distribution of powers in the management system increased the effectiveness of decision-making;

- the introduction of digital platforms has formed a culture of data-driven management;

- the improvement of the qualifications of teachers and managers contributed to the growth of the quality of education;

- public participation ensured the openness of management.

At the same time, the main task for the future is to enrich management with innovative mechanisms, implement digital infrastructure in all regions, increase personnel potential, and adapt the content of education to the requirements of the labor market. This will form a competitive, effective, and humane management model for the education system of New Uzbekistan - a solid foundation for the country's long-term sustainable development.

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